

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.358 Max: 63.016	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1473 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic
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In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 2141-2144 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *construction cut for wall 1474*

Covered by SU: 1474 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%		
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive		
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash			
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells			
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)				
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass					
			Compaction	Color	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow	
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1474	Covers: n.w.
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *dry, sunny conditions, SU has not been excavated in 2011*

DESCRIPTION: *at the southern edge of Trench B 2011*

Position within sector:

Shape: *long rectangular*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations: *not excavated yet*

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

The sketch shows a cross-section of the site. A north arrow points upwards. A large layer labeled '1473' is at the top, containing a 'grave 1347'. Below it are layers 1474, 1468, and 1393. A horizontal layer labeled '1415' is shown, with a '1474' label below it. Below 1415 is layer 1390. Further down are layers 1471, 1472, and 1448. On the right side, there are layers 1411 and 1387. On the left side, there are layers 1414, 1400, 1391, and 1421. A 'Via Cloud' is indicated on the far left. Elevation markers include 1469 at the top right and 1474 near the grave.

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Construction cut, filled with large stones and sandy soil.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	<i>CMM</i>	on	<i>3.8.2011</i>
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